

Thiourea and its Organic Derivatives. Part IV. Oxidimetric Determination with Chloramine-T

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Chloramine-T has been used as a redox reagent for visual and potentiometric determinations of thiourea and its several alkyl and aryl derivatives in sulphuric acid medium.

The thioureas are oxidised in presence of potassium iodide to the corresponding disulphides with a single electron change:

This direct method is simple, accurate, and instantaneous.

Afanas'ev¹ determined thiourea with chloramine-T in hot dilute sulphuric acid, using methyl orange as an indicator. Singh *et al.*² carried out a potentiometric titration of thiourea with chloramine-T in sulphuric acid at 80°. Thiourea is oxidised to carbonic acid, sulphuric acid, and water under these conditions. Berka and Zyka³ reported that the direct potentiometric titration of thiourea with chloramine-T was possible in presence of potassium bromide in acid solution.

During our preliminary experiments it has been found that in presence of potassium iodide, chloramine-T smoothly oxidises thioureas at room temperature. This direct method, which affords both the visual and the potentiometric determinations of thioureas, is simple, accurate, and instantaneous. In previous communications⁴, Singh *et al.* have shown that the thioureas are oxidised to the corresponding disulphides with iodine monochloride, iodine trichloride, and diethylenetetra-ammonium sulphatocerate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chloramine-T was prepared by the method described by Vogel⁵. The compound (7.5 g.) was dissolved in water and the volume made to one litre. The solution was standardised by an iodometric method and kept in the dark.

Visual Method.—A known weight (10 to 70 mg.) of each compound was taken in a titration flask. In case of thiourea and its alkyl derivatives, sufficient water and enough

1. *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1949, 15, 1271.

2. *Res. Bull. (N.S.) Panjab Univ.*, 1953, 30, 55.

3. *Chekoslov. Farmac.* 1956, 5, 335.

4. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 211, 490; 1963, 40, 39.

5. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", published by Longmans, Green and Co., London, 3rd ed., 1956, p. 822.

of H_2SO_4 were added to keep normality of the solution at 1*N*. Each aryl derivative of thiourea was dissolved in 18*N*- H_2SO_4 (10 to 12 ml) and sufficient water (35 to 72 ml) was added to keep normality of the solution at 2.5 to 4.0*N*. Potassium iodide (0.4 ml, 10% soln.) was added in each case except in the cases of *o*-tolyl-, *o*-methoxyphenyl-, and *o*-ethoxyphenyl-thioureas, where 0.1 ml of 10% potassium iodide solution was added. The solution was cooled to room temperature and titrated with standard (*N*/20) chloramine-T. End point in each case was detected visually as well as potentiometrically. In visual titrations amylose (0.2 ml of 1% soln.) was added as an indicator and the solution acquired a blue colour at the end point.

Potentiometric Method.—A platinum wire electrode, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode and this was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The solution was kept stirred by a mechanical stirrer during the titration. At the equivalence point there was a sharp jump in potential in each case. A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amount of each substance.

From the volume of standard (*N*/20) chloramine-T solution used, corresponding to the end point in each titration, the amount of thiourea or each of its organic derivatives was calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds,	Visual method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
N- $CR_3CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2NH.CS.NH_2$	0.0120 g.	0.0120 g.	0.0134 g.	0.0133 g.
	0.0210	0.0211	0.0280	0.0280
	0.0295	0.0295	0.0343	0.0341
	0.0342	0.0344	0.0401	0.0400
	0.0515	0.0516	0.0528	0.0526
<i>o</i> -(OCH_3) $C_6H_4NH.CS.NH_2$	0.0278	0.0278	0.0244	0.0243
	0.0350	0.0350	0.0302	0.0301
	0.0393	0.0392	0.0356	0.0358
	0.0432	0.0433	0.0425	0.0425
	0.0548	0.0548	0.0545	0.0546
$(CH_3)_2CHCH_2NH.CS.NH_2$	0.0135	0.0135	0.0138	0.0138
	0.0214	0.0215	0.0202	0.0200
	0.0325	0.0325	0.0250	0.0250
	0.0396	0.0396	0.0287	0.0285
	0.0510	0.0511	0.0520	0.0520
<i>o</i> -(OC_2H_5) $C_6H_4NH.CS.NH_2$	0.0184	0.0184	0.0194	0.0194
	0.0275	0.0275	0.0300	0.0302
	0.0263	0.0363	0.0395	0.0397
	0.0440	0.0442	0.0500	0.0498
	0.0581	0.0582	0.0613	0.0614
$NH_2.CS.NH_2$	0.0190	0.0190	0.0142	0.0143
	0.0304	0.0304	0.0190	0.0191
	0.0380	0.0381	0.0250	0.0251
	0.0456	0.0456	0.0304	0.0305
	0.0570	0.0570	0.0380	0.0381

TABLE I (contd.)

Compounds.	Visual method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
<i>o</i> -(CH ₃) ₆ H ₄ NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0152	0.0152	0.0211	0.0210
	0.0243	0.0243	0.0307	0.0306
	0.0336	0.0337	0.0398	0.0397
	0.0465	0.0465	0.0501	0.0501
	0.0592	0.0593	0.0617	0.0617
<i>n</i> -(CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0143	0.0143	0.0200	0.0200
	0.0262	0.0262	0.0273	0.0271
	0.0341	0.0342	0.0306	0.0306
	0.0453	0.0454	0.0398	0.0399
	0.0501	0.0501	0.0434	0.0434
(CH ₃) ₂ CHNH.CS.NH ₂	0.0227	0.0227	0.0210	0.0210
	0.0372	0.0372	0.0310	0.0311
	0.0491	0.0490	0.0435	0.0436
	0.0532	0.0530	0.0525	0.0523
	0.0600	0.0601	0.0627	0.0625
CH ₃ CH ₂ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0125	0.0125	0.0204	0.0205
	0.0234	0.0234	0.0336	0.0336
	0.0312	0.0312	0.0382	0.0383
	0.0400	0.0402	0.0431	0.0429
	0.0509	0.0510	0.0528	0.0525
CH ₃ NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0150	0.0150	0.0190	0.0190
	0.0265	0.0265	0.0233	0.0233
	0.0343	0.0344	0.0321	0.0320
	0.0429	0.0430	0.0380	0.0377
	0.0524	0.0524	0.0528	0.0528
<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₆ H ₄ NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0110	0.0110	..	..
	0.0200	0.0202	..	..
	0.0250	0.0252	..	..
	0.0298	0.0300	..	..
	0.0347	0.0348	..	..
<i>p</i> -(OCH ₃) ₆ H ₄ .NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0220	0.0220	..	..
	0.0300	0.0300	..	..
	0.0373	0.0374	..	..
	0.0406	0.0408	..	..
	0.0510	0.0512	..	..
<i>p</i> -(OC ₂ H ₅) ₆ H ₄ NH.CS.NH ₂	0.0210	0.0210	..	..
	0.0270	0.0271	..	..
	0.0300	0.0299	..	..
	0.0347	0.0345	..	..
	0.0395	0.0397	..	..

The results recorded in the table show that the listed compounds can be determined by direct titration with chloramine-T in presence of potassium iodide in sulphuric acid medium.

The authors thank the Ministry of Education, Government of India, for the award of a research training scholarship to one of them (B.C.V.).